

DOES VIOLATING THE WILLIAMS ACT CONSTITUTE UNETHICAL CONDUCT? AN EXAMINATION OF AN OVERLOOKED ETHICAL ISSUE IN CORPORATE TAKEOVER LAW & POLICY

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Abstract

The Williams Act makes it more difficult and costly for a raider to acquire the target company in a hostile takeover. In this article the author examines whether violating the Williams Act constitutes unethical conduct using several ethical approaches. The conclusion is that violating the Williams Act does not automatically constitute unethical conduct. Whether violating the Williams Act constitutes unethical conduct depends on how the Act is violated.

Introduction

The law places obstacles in the path of tender offers that hinders their success and efficiency.² One such law that works in

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² Gregg A. Jarrell and Michael Bradley, *The Economic Effects of Federal and State Regulations on Cash Tender Offers*, 23 JOURNAL OF LAW & ECONOMICS 371 (1980), cited in RICHARD A. POSNER, *ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF LAW* (5TH ED. 1998), at 454.

this manner is the Williams Act. The Williams Act was enacted by Congress in 1968 to regulate tender offers.³ To be more specific, the Act requires raiders to give advance warning that they are going to attack and requires them to disclose other detailed information as well. Anyone who acquires, directly or indirectly, a five-percent beneficial interest in a certain security must disclose detailed information outlining his background, identity, source of funds and acquisition plans. The number of shares owned and any agreements between the acquirer and other persons must also be disclosed. The party acquiring five percent must disclose the information to the target company, the Securities and Exchange Commission and the exchange where the stock is being traded. Once the offer is announced, the offeror may not make purchases other than through the tender offer. Open market purchases (at a lower price) are forbidden.

Acquisitions and Mergers

Acquisitions and mergers are beneficial for a number of individuals and groups. The old shareholders benefit because they receive a premium for their stock. New shareholders benefit because they are buying into a company that is about to become more efficient and competitive. Nontendering shareholders benefit because their stock increases in value as a result of the tender offer. Society benefits because a restructured, lean and efficient company provides higher quality goods and services at lower prices. Employees benefit because a healthy company provides more job security than a weak, noncompetitive, inefficient company.⁴

³ 15 U.S.C. §§78m(d)-(e), 78n(d)(f) (1982 & Supp. III 1985). Ostensibly, the drafters of the Williams Act wanted it to be neutral in effect as between target company management and the offerors. Some corporate raiders would disagree with that assessment of the Act. See S. Rep. No. 550, 90th Cong., 1st Sess. (1967).

⁴ There is some evidence to suggest that hostile takeovers have a beneficial effect on wages and employment. See Charles Brown and James L. Medoff, *The Impact of Firm Acquisitions on Labor*, National Bureau of Economic Research, May, 1987.

Even an unsuccessful takeover⁵ attempt can cause these groups to benefit because the mere threat of a takeover often causes management to become better managers. The only group that stands to lose as a result of an acquisition or merger is top management, which stands to be replaced if the takeover is successful. Thus, it follows that attempts to prevent takeovers reduce the welfare of all these groups, with the exception of management, which stands to gain by thwarting a takeover attempt.

Many of the ethical problems connected with takeovers relate to top management's attempt to prevent their company from being taken over. Management has a fiduciary duty to act in the best interest of shareholders, yet a successful takeover will often result in some members of top management losing their jobs and perhaps forcing them into early retirement. Given this scenario, there is tremendous pressure on top management to breach their fiduciary duty and pull out all stops to either prevent a takeover attempt from being successful or make plans to cushion their fall in the event the takeover attempt is successful.

The Williams Act

The Williams Act gives the target company shareholders the right to withdraw their tendered shares within seven days after the tender offer is published or within 60 days from the date the original offer was made. This deadline has been extended by the

⁵ A takeover is a:

..."change in the controlling interest of a corporation. A takeover may be a friendly acquisition or an unfriendly bid that the TARGET COMPANY may fight with SHARK REPELLENT techniques. A hostile takeover (aiming to replace existing management) is usually attempted through a public TENDER OFFER. Other approaches might be unsolicited merger proposals to directors, accumulations of shares in the open market, or PROXY FIGHTS that seek to install new directors." *DICTIONARY OF FINANCE AND INVESTMENT TERMS* (JOHN DOWNES AND JORDAN ELLIOT GOODMAN, EDS., 5TH ED. 1998), at 618.

Securities and Exchange Commission to 15 business days from the start of the offer and 10 business days from the start of any competing offer, provided the original raider knows about the competing offer and has not accepted the shares the shareholders seek to withdraw. If the offer is for less than all the shares of a particular class and the shareholders are willing to offer more shares than the offeror is willing to purchase, the offeror must purchase the shares on a pro rata basis rather than first-come, first-served.

Originally, the Williams Act proration requirement applied only to shares tendered within the first ten days of the offer, but the Securities and Exchange Commission later extended the allowable time to the entire offer period. If the raider increases consideration during the offer period, all tendering shareholders are entitled to receive the same deal -- the highest price offered. The Williams Act also prohibits any untrue statements or material omission of facts, or any fraudulent, deceptive or manipulative acts or practices.

Since acquisitions and mergers are good for the economy in general,⁶ and for target company shareholders in particular, it

⁶ There are exceptions, of course, but the evidence is clear that acquisitions and mergers are generally good for the economy and for shareholders because they tend to increase stock price and efficiency. For more on this point, see Robert W. McGee, *Ethical Issues in Acquisitions and Mergers*, COMMENTARIES ON THE LAW OF ACCOUNTING & FINANCE (1998); Robert W. McGee, *The Economics of Mergers and Acquisitions*, 25 MID-ATLANTIC JOURNAL OF BUSINESS (Feb. 1989); Michael C. Jensen, *Takeovers: Their Causes and Consequences*, 2 JOURNAL OF ECONOMIC PERSPECTIVES 21-48 (Winter, 1988); Michael C. Jensen and Richard S. Ruback, *The Market for Corporate Control: The Scientific Evidence*, 11 JOURNAL OF FINANCIAL ECONOMICS 5-50 (1983); Michael C. Jensen, *The Efficiency of Takeovers*, THE CORPORATE BOARD 16-22 (Sept. - Oct. 1985); Michael C. Jensen, *The Takeover Controversy: Analysis and Evidence*, 4 MIDLAND CORPORATION FINANCE JOURNAL (Summer, 1986); Michael C. Jensen, *Takeovers: folklore and science*, 62 HARVARD BUSINESS REVIEW 109-121 (Nov. - Dec. 1984); Michael C. Jensen, *Agency Costs of Free Cash Flow, Corporate Finance, and Takeovers*, 76 AMERICAN ECONOMIC REVIEW 323-329 (May 1986); Paul J. Halpern, *Empirical Estimates of the Amount and Distribution of Gains to Companies in Mergers*, 46 JOURNAL OF

seems logical that government should promote such activity, or at least not place artificial hurdles in the way of consenting adults who want to enter into such activity. Yet it appears that the Williams Act is one of those hurdles. The Act is aimed at reducing the number of tender offers made, and increasing the cost of those that are made. Raiders must give advance warning of their intent, which gives entrenched management the opportunity to thwart the takeover bid. Once the declaration to acquire is made, the raider can no longer purchase shares on the open market, where they are cheaper. A premium must be paid on all shares subsequently acquired. If the shares are acquired at more than one price, the raider must later make up the price differential to those shareholders who willingly sold at a lower price before.

Once the decision is made to acquire the target company, it is in the raider's best interest to acquire as many shares as possible before the word hits the street that the acquisition is being made. The Williams Act limits the number of shares that the raider can acquire before making its intentions known, which both places a chilling effect on acquisition activity and drives up the cost of any acquisition attempt. Both the shareholders and the raider are harmed by this result.⁷ The shareholders are harmed because they

BUSINESS 554-575 (Oct. 1973); Frank H. Easterbrook and Daniel R. Fischel, *The Proper Role of a Target's Management in Responding to a Tender Offer*, 94 HARVARD LAW REVIEW 1161-1204 (April, 1981); Douglas H. Ginsburg and John F. Robinson, *The Case Against Federal Intervention in the Market for Corporate Control*, BROOKINGS REVIEW 9-14 (Winter/Spring, 1986); Glenn Yago and Gelvin Stevenson, *Mergers and Acquisitions in the New Jersey Economy*, sponsored by the Securities Industry Association and published by the Economic Research Bureau, State University of New York at Stony Brook, May 8, 1986.

⁷ Actually, target company shareholders can benefit if the attempt is successful because they receive the benefit of the higher price the raider must pay for the stock. But by artificially raising the stock price, the Williams Act also decreases the probability of a successful takeover, so target company shareholders stand to lose as a result. For some studies that measure the cost of takeover regulation, see Paul Asquith, Robert F. Bruner and David W. Mullins, Jr., *The Gains to Bidding Firms from Merger*, 11 JOURNAL OF FINANCIAL ECONOMICS (1983);

stand to benefit if the acquisition attempt is successful. The raider loses because the disclosure rule drives up the cost of the acquisition and makes it less attractive. If successful, the raider will make the company operate more efficiently, which is good for the company, consumers and shareholders. Inefficient management that the shareholders cannot get rid of (because they are entrenched) can be replaced by a management team that does a better job. Preventing such events from happening hurts just about everyone except the target company's present management.

Before the Williams Act, potential raiders could gather together to formulate a plan in secret. They would place tender offer ads in the major newspapers over the weekend and when the newspapers hit the stands they would be ready to buy. They could make the offer good for a very short time, such as a week, and they would know whether their takeover attempt was successful within a matter of days. The high interest charges they have to pay on the borrowed money used for the takeover could be kept to a minimum. But with the extended offer terms required by the Williams Act, the interest charges keep mounting over a much longer time period, thus driving up the cost of the acquisition attempt and reducing the takeover's chance of success.

The Williams Act caused corporate raiders to change the way they do business. Raiders had to find out how many shares they could acquire at a given price before actually making their intent known to the public, so risk arbitrageurs gave them a helping hand by prepositioning or warehousing blocks of shares before the tender offer was made public. Their actions might have taken place

Gregg Jarrell and Michael Bradley, *The Economic Effects of Federal and State Regulations of Cash Tender Offers*, 23 JOURNAL OF LAW & ECONOMICS 371-407 (1980); Katherine Schipper and Rex Thompson, *Evidence on the Capitalized Value of Merger Activity for Acquiring Firms*, 11 JOURNAL OF FINANCIAL ECONOMICS (1983); Robert Smiley, *The Effect of the Williams Amendment and Other Factors on Transactions Costs in Tender Offers*, 3 INDUSTRIAL ORGANIZATION REVIEW 138-145 (1975). For a summary of these studies, see Michael C. Jensen and Richard S. Ruback, *The Market for Corporate Control: The Scientific Evidence*, 11 JOURNAL OF FINANCIAL ECONOMICS 5-50 (1983) at 28-29.

with or without collusion, but the fact that arbitrageurs make the chances of a successful takeover more likely should be noted. These so-called dealers in insider information benefit the economy by helping to make takeover bids successful, and successful takeover bids, as has been demonstrated, are good for the economy. As one critic of the Williams Act has stated:

The tender offer is the most important and beneficial financial invention of the 20th century. Its very existence has probably added hundreds of billions of dollars to American capital values. Without it, noncontrolling shareholders in companies with widely diffused ownership would be nearly helpless in the face of managerial incompetence, self-dealing or inattention to business.⁸

Ethical Approaches

There are basically two ethical approaches that can be taken to determine whether violating the Williams Act constitutes unethical conduct -- utilitarianism and rights theory. Utilitarianism is the ethical philosophy espoused by the vast majority of economists so we will start by applying utilitarian theory to the question. Basically, utilitarianism aims at the greatest good for the greatest number. Jeremy Bentham, an early proponent of the utilitarian philosophy, said that "...it is the greatest happiness of the greatest number that is the measure of right and wrong."⁹ Henry Sidgwick, a later utilitarian, extends the philosophy, as follows:

⁸ Henry G. Manne, *The Real Boesky-Case Issue*, THE NEW YORK TIMES, November 25, 1986, A-27, column 1.

⁹ Jeremy Bentham, *A fragment on government*, in THE WORKS OF JEREMY BENTHAM, VOL. 1 227 (J. BOWRING, ED., 1962), as quoted in WILLIAM H. SHAW, CONTEMPORARY ETHICS: TAKING ACCOUNT OF UTILITARIANISM 8 (1999).

...an action is right if and only if it brings about at least as much net happiness as any other action the agent could have performed; otherwise it is wrong.¹⁰

According to Sidgwick's view, an act that increases happiness by 10 percent is unethical if another act could have increased happiness by more than 10 percent.¹¹ Richard A. Posner, one of the leaders of the law and economics movement, seems to indicate that an act is moral if it is efficient.¹² From his view, one may perhaps draw an inference that an act is immoral if it increases inefficiency.¹³

The Williams Act makes acquisitions and mergers less likely and more costly. Thus, it increases inefficiency and decreases happiness. From a utilitarian point of view, the Williams Act is unethical. Since the Act is unethical, violating the Act would seemingly constitute ethical conduct, at least in cases where efficiency or happiness increases as a result of the violation.

The other tool of ethical analysis is right theory. Rights theory, properly conceived, begins with the nonaggression axiom: "No man or group of men may aggress against the person or property of anyone else."¹⁴ In the realm of economics, this means that no man or group of men (including government) may prevent consenting adults from entering into contracts and trading the

¹⁰ Quoted in SHAW, *supra*, at 10.

¹¹ There are several problems with the utilitarian philosophy, such as the inability to measure changes in happiness and the fact that utilitarianism totally ignores rights violations. For more on this point, see Robert W. McGee, *The Fatal Flaw in the Methodology of Law and Economics*, COMMENTARIES ON LAW & ECONOMICS 209-223 (1997).

¹² RICHARD A. POSNER, *ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF LAW* 284-285 (5TH ED. 1998).

¹³ A variation on the utilitarian theme is the wealth maximization view, which holds that "...the criterion for judging whether acts and institutions are just or good is whether they maximize the wealth of society." RICHARD A. POSNER, *THE ECONOMICS OF JUSTICE* 115 (1983).

¹⁴ MURRAY N. ROTHBARD, *FOR A NEW LIBERTY* 23 (1978).

property they have for the property they want. That is not to say that all acts between consenting adults are ethical. Some such acts may be unethical, like selling addictive drugs, prostitution, etc. The nonaggression axiom merely states that such voluntary exchanges should not be prevented.

The Williams Act prevents the free exchange of shares of stock. It also forcibly alters the terms of trade, since it forces potential purchasers of stock to disclose much information that is no one's business. The Williams Act violates the nonaggression axiom. Thus, it is unethical from a rights perspective. Whether it is unethical to violate an unethical law depends on the law in question. If prostitution is unethical, then violating the laws against prostitution by engaging in this activity constitutes unethical conduct even though laws that prohibit prostitution are themselves unethical. But violating a law that prevents consenting adults from voluntarily buying and selling shares of stock does not seem to constitute unethical conduct. No one's rights are violated by the voluntary buying and selling of shares. Thus, according to rights theory, there is nothing unethical about buying and selling shares even if it violates the Williams Act.

Concluding Comments

The Williams Act prohibits any untrue statements or material omission of facts, or any fraudulent, deceptive or manipulative acts or practices.¹⁵ Anyone who violates any of these prohibitions is guilty of unethical conduct. However, these prohibitions are the only occasions when violating the Williams Act constitutes unethical conduct.

The Williams Act protects an entrenched, inefficient minority at the expense of shareholders. It does so by abusing governmental power. It is a classic case of rent-seeking. The Williams Act increases inefficiency and raises the cost of a successful takeover. It also reduces the probability of a successful

¹⁵ So do several other laws. If the Williams Act were repealed, the public would still be protected from such activities.

takeover. Thus, the Act itself is unethical from a utilitarian standpoint.

The Act is also unethical from a rights perspective because it violates the rights to property and contract. Consenting adults cannot freely enter into contracts and trade the property they have for the property they want. Government dictates at what price exchanges can take place and even whether exchanges can take place. The law forces the raider to disclose information that the target company's board of directors have no right to know. Thus, there are also elements of violations of free speech, since speech is forced.

Since the Williams Act protects entrenched management at the expense of shareholders, harms the economy and consumers in general and increases the price corporate raiders must pay, the logical step would be to repeal it. Yet some Senators want to see tender offer regulations tightened, an action that would make the situation worse than it already is. Before Congress starts changing the law, it should be very careful to determine what the possible effects on various groups would be. Based on recent speeches by Senators and members of Congress, it appears that Congress has not yet done that.